

(7) kaḷa āturayan bat no (8) genae esu waḷan koṭ (9) bat gannā dasa

135. Dewanagala.—Siriwat apiriyat lo ikut guṇa mulin uturat wū Damba (2) diwuhi an kaet kula paemili kaḷa Okāwas parapuren baṭ (3) kaeta usabnaṭ agamehesun wū Lak diwu poḷoyogen parapuren himi (4) tumā sarāṇa tisara sin gat raja mudun wisesa wū sāha tedin hira (5) paḷa kelin mehesu radol daewin daewiṇa raja wīra

137. Galwihāra, Polonnaruwa. — Apa Budun kalpa ḷata sahasrādhika caturasa [m] khyaparimitakālayen sama tisa param purā Māra saṅgrāmbhūmi wū maḷabodhi pa [r] yyam-kārūḍha wāe durwwāra sapa

(2.) riwāra Māra parājaya koṭae sarwwajñāpada prāpta wae pansālis hawuruddak dawas caturthi pak mahā meghayak seyin waeḍae siṭae ane

(3.) kakalpa koṭi ḷata sahasrayehi keḷeḷāḷanin da sewemin siṭi satyayan dharmmāmṛitawarshāyen niwamin sakala Buddha kṛitya ninawā Kusinārā nuwarae abiyeshi Ma

(4.) Ila rājayange sālwanodyā [na] yehi nirupadhiḷesha nirwwāna dhātuwen diwi niwi sāra siya supanaes hawuruddak giya kalae Waḷagam Abhā mahā rāja dawasae paṭan ekwā dahas su

(5.) panaes hawuruddak bhinna nikāya wae ḷāsanaya piriwemin siṭi kalhi Mahāsammataḍi paramparāyāta sūryayawaṇḷodhbhūta rājāḍhirāja naikadigabhiwyāpta yaḷomariḷin wirājamāna

(6.) Ḷrī Saṅghabodhi Parākramabāhu maharajāṇan sakala Lamkātelehi ekarāyābhishekayen abhisikta wae wijrim-bhitapunyaṛddhi aeti wae rājyasukhānubhawa koṭae waḍanuwan

(7.) aḷjāna durjūāna mūlaka apratipatti dushpratipatti wisha wega wihata wae apāyānnawana ḷāsanāwacara kula-putrayan daekae supariḷuddha Buddha ḷāsanayehi māwaeni aḷjā ca

(8.) krawarttiyak hu me . . la ni kiluṭak daekae udāsina wuwa hot Budu sasna nassi boho sat hudu apāya bhāg weti pas wā dahasak pawatnā Budu sasnaṭa mā wahal wuwa maenaewaeyi

(9.) prajūā purassara karuṇāyen saṇcodita hṛidaya aeti w [ae] dosena warjḷun kawurun wahalkoṭa apāgata kaḷamka wae pas wā dahasak pawatnā paridden kerem do hoyi siṭa akhaṇḷacchidratāḍi wiwi

(10.) dha guṇa gaṇāṅga saṅgata koṭae rakshita warddhita poshita ḷila skandhāḍi laukika guṇa ratnālamkārāyen samalamkṛita wū Udumbara giri niwāsi mahā Kāḷyapa mahā sthawira pramukha mahāwihārāḍhiwāsi

(11.) bhikshu saṅghayā daekae owun wahal koṭae Budun wisin anujūāta Buddha kalpa Moggaliputtis mahaterun wahal koṭae pāpabhikshu nirmmaḷa naya koṭae dullabayi maeḷae ḷāsana ma

(12.) la wiḥodhā tṛitīya dharmmasaṅgāyana kaeraewū Dharm-māçoka maharajahu me [n] anekaçata pāpa bhikshūn çāstra-çāsanayen apagata koṭae shaḍ abhijñādyaneka guṇa gaṇopeta mahākshīnā

(13.) çrawayan aeti kalhi pawāhaya rājayan wisin mahot-sāhayenudu samaṅga no koṭae gatahuṇu tun nakā samaṅga kirī-men ek nakā koṭae jetawana mahāwihārādi no ek maha aegi wi

(14.) hāra Lak diwae tanhi tanhi karawā ehi sahasra samkhyātīkrānta maha sam [gha] yāwāsa karawā nirantara prawṛitta dharmmāmisha dānayen upasthāna keremin samghadarçana prabhawa pṛiti prāmodya rasā

(15.) swādayehi lola wae kālānukālayehi paushathāṅgaçīla samāpto wae wihārayaṭa eḷabae sannipatita samgha madhya gata wae tad darçana prasūta pṛiti prāmodya rasās-wāda koṭae mā wisin mahotsā

(16.) hayen sākāt wū me samghāma çriya pas wā dahasak abhinna wae pawatnā paridden matu wana samghayā da apramāda wae widarçanā dhuraḷayehi yodī alepa cajātādi guṇen yukta wae waḍanā paridden

(17.) awawādānuçāsana koṭae çāsanaya rakshā kaḷa maenaewaeyi yukta wyakta guṇopeta waekarana ārādhanā da asā Mahā Kāçyapa mahā sthawira pramukha sthawirawarayan mae wisi

(18.) n pramāda wihārīn awakāça no labana sandahā dharm-mawinaya sandahā koṭae ādurol da no wihidae kaḷa katikāwati . . . gaṇadeṭu terawarun wisin tamatamā nisā wana antewāsika saddhiwi

(19.) hārikayan aturehi nisadennāṭa nisayen mindennāṭa yogya wae wasannawun pamā no wiyae dī grantha dhurayehi yodā yaetāt piriseyin winayen kudu sikha hā pāmok da suttin da sadham sūtratraya anumāna

(20.) sūtra sadā wanapot piriheḷiyae no dī gaṇa samgaṇī-kādīn duru koṭa grantha dhurayehi (yehi) yedennawun wisin udu satatayen wiweka wat piraewa maenaewaeyi wadāḷa baewin tun welehi i

(21.) riya eka manā siṭi pirişudu koṭae kāgiyā si ādi wū kamaṭa hanekhi yedī de tun palahak huṇu ganwā dawasakaḍa no koṭa wiweka wat purawā attānam ewa paḍhama parirūpe nivesaye yi wadāḷa baewin tama

(22.) tamā da me ki guṇaṅgayehi weselin yedī at waedā parawaedā sādhamin kī paridden granthadhurayen waediyak koṭa gata no hena antewāsika saddhi-wihārikayan lawā mul sikha sekhiya wana

(23.) pot karawā sikha waḷanda winisa aswā samasin samasae ādyanta koṭae samanā wicāḷa taenaeka kiyannaṭa pohosat karawā dasadham satatayen menehi karawā yaetā ki wiwekawat udu

(24.) purawā çak [ti] pamaṇak hadārā nimi kalae caritānukūla kamaṭa hatak uganwā widarçanā dhurayehi mā yodā catu sampajamku kathāyehi wadāḷa paridden dawas yawanu koṭae paewaetwiyae yutu

mahallawun no danwa mehe karuwanta daehawili no wiyae yutu tamā ayati yakaduru bhallan anu no danwa an

(40.) nata no diyae yutu gasan yan nak . . hu wisin mahalu saṅgun genemī nasnata sudusu prikarakara athi aeta mut aturehi waesi awalawiya wigaranin mae no temen taen elaebiyae yutu ebandu pi

(41.) rikaraka çatasaruwan we . . . la wiyekin maeyāe yutu nawa y[u]t[u] e tuna gana tu [m] wewa niki da ta watu . . . smi hasa nisa samī mihita mattanta vaddhati yī wadāla baewin sināwata nisi karanek

(42.) hi duhasa no wihidae muwa wasae satuṭu pamaṅak daekwiyae yutu tamā wana wehera sanhindaena ayi karaṅa baehaera no wahalakata yutu an weherae sanhindaena ayi karaṅa tamā no ne siṭiyae yutu ka

(43.) l lekha asamjantena apamattena bhikkhunā kṛippiye win kaeta bā āmisatvāya lolatā yī wadāla baewin kaepa passehi du lol baw no kaṭa yutu dahagab mahāambo aē wandimi

(44.) n ganda dukha aē pudamin daewuṭu walandamin pākassehi lamīna no biṅiyae yutu aetgambi gīhi minisun hā wa sa piḷibada kathā da wisabhāgakathā da no kaṭa yutu idhekasō samghaga

(45.) to pi acittikāra katā there bhikkhū ghaṭṭhayanto pi tiṭṭhati saṭṭhayanto pi nisidati dvijako (?) pi bhaṅati byahyā-tike bapako pi bhaṅati kumārassa pī siram parāmasati yī anyata

(46.) ra nidesahi wadāla baewin saṅga maendata elaebiyā hu wisin udu werin ew siwuren ciwa no ghaṭṭiyae yutu mahalu saṅgun hā biṅuwa manā karuṅaka āta ādara dakwā itā no lawae naemi siṭae sa

(47.) t no wanā biṅiyae yutu kisi taenekhi du komarun werae at lā no saenaewiyae yutu padhan gherehi wasanu wanaṭa wikhewa no koṭae hādaēriyae yutu pabbājentā sodhetvā pabbāje

(48.) tha sodhetvā upasampādettha sodhetvā nissayam detha eko pi hi kulaputto pabbajaṅca upasampadaṅca labhitvā salamaṭi sāsanam patitṭhāpeti yū baewin piriksā paewiji kaṭa yutu pirik

(49.) sā upasampatti kaṭa yutu piriksā nisidiyae yutu kamāya han pamaṅak durbhaṅga samādan wiyae yutu meki tāk watae no risin pawatuk udu ayuṅu no kīyae yutu yam kenek me kaḷa katikā

(50.) wathi no hikmae waradata pawatit nam tun yaelak dakwā waradata nisi danḍuwam karawā awawāda koṭae naewaetae da ese mae pawatit nam nisi no dī masak dakwā hinduwā winayānukula paewae

(51.) tinak naeta hot un kerehi no baendi haeraewiyae yutu ganadeṭu terawarun wisin udu taman tanaṭa yedū dhurayehi pamā wae samghāyā hikmawā no lu lāt hot mahaterawarun yedū da[n]duwam kaṭa yutu . . çrī

138. Galāṅdawala :—Çrī siri saṅgabo Parākramabā (2) hu wat himiyan wahanse e (3) me wātā walamaṭa wadāla galla (4) rīm asārā hengayen maeta ta (5) . . rae waellen maetae hā meki hi

hall, the two washermen that wash the clothes, the vestments, and the bed-linen, shall get three kiriyas from Magulwaewa. In the villages and lands belonging to this temple the roads and high roads shall be taken, wanderers and pilgrims shall not enter. So much water as is in the tank shall be distributed to the wihāra lands in the manner formerly regulated by the Tamils. None of the lands belonging to this temple shall be given away as a pledge, those who have thus gotten any thereof shall give it back to the temple. To ensure prosperity to the institution these regulations shall be strictly obeyed.

(123.) Mineri : the workmen on the fields, if there is any work a fine of 500 kalandas of gold the noblemen shall take in this kingdom, cocoanuts and tamarinds shall not be cut inside the three kingdoms shall not stand the warder of the granary with one hand five the fifth

(124.) Attanayāla : The glorious endless who was an object of respect to the Kshatriya tribe, being descended from the unbroken line of Ikshwāku, being born in the womb of the chief queen to His Majesty the King, son of King Siri saṅga bo, the pinnacle of the Kshatriya castle, the sage who learned the doctrine

(129.) Slab from Anurādhapura : The lay devotees to the lords of the world of gold two hanas and a half, one admana at the two corners flowers sick people shall not take rice, having made bracelets for them, to take rice

(135.) Dewanagala : The glorious endless, whose renown extended over the whole world, who was an object of veneration to the other royal dynasties of Dambadiwa, descended from the uninterrupted line of the Ikshwāku family, an eminent Kshatriya, born in the womb of the chief queen, who had become Lord of Lankā by (hereditary) succession

(137.) Galwihāra, Polonnaruwa : 1254 years from the time of King Waḷagam Abhā, when 454 years had elapsed since our Buddha, having, in a time extending over four asankhya's 100,000 kalpa's, fulfilled all the thirty perfections, and having, on the Māra battle-ground, mounted on the divan of thorough enlightenment, conquered the irresistible Māra, together with his retinue, attained the state of omniscience, and forty-five years (after that), on the fourth day, having accomplished by quenching as a large cloud does by rain, so he, in many hundred thousands of crores of kalpas, by the nectar of the law [having thus accomplished] all the duties of a Buddha, extinguished (his) life by means of the sacred nirupadhiṣsha nirvāṇa near the city of Kuṣinagara, in the grove of Sāl trees of the king of the Malla's when, the congregations being broken up, religion was fading away, His Majesty King Çri Saṅghabodhi Parākramabāhu, descended from the unbroken line of Mahāsammata and the others, born of the Solar race, the king

over kings, resplendent through the rays of his glory, which has penetrated many regions, anointed by the anointment of paramount dominion on Laṃkā's ground, enjoying the delight of dominion with the treasure of his merits made patent, he, the very wise one, having removed the powerful poison of non-observance and false observance of religious ordinances (which are) the root of ignorance and false knowledge, having seen young gentlemen practising religion (thinking): if, seeing a spot on of an emperor like me in the religion of the pure Buddha, they might become indifferent, then Buddha's religion will be destroyed, and many beings go to hell, (therefore) it is right that I shall support the religion of Buddha in order that it may last five thousand (years) like Dhammāsoka, who, his heart instigated by compassion preceded by intelligence, having supported the thinking I will make that it lasts spotless for five thousand (years), having combined a number of virtues as unbrokenness and freeness from holes, having seen the congregation of priests living in the great wihāra under the leadership of the great Sthavira Mahākācyapa, who lived on Udumbara giri, ornated with the jewel ornament of wordly qualities as preservation, increase and cultivation of the aggregates of virtues, &c., having supported them, having supported the great thera Tissa, son of Moggali, who was granted a Buddhakalpa by Buddha, having made the wicked Bhikshus behave spotlessly, having crushed what resisted, having cleansed from dirt the religion, had caused the third council—removed many hundred wicked Bhikshus from the teaching and religion, having made one nikāya by uniting the three nikāya's, which even at the time when there were great Arhats endowed with a number of qualities as the six supernatural faculties, &c., not being united even with great effort by former kings, were having built the great wihāra of Jetāwana and many other costly wihāras in various places in the island of Laṃkā, having made there residences for more than thousand of the great priesthood, making support by the gift of the food of the religion uninterruptedly continued being desirous of the enjoyment of the taste of the happiness rising from the sight of the priesthood—having from time to time adopted the vow of fasting, having approached the wihāra and gone among the priests assembled,—having enjoyed the taste of the happiness of the joy produced by this sight (thinking): it is right that by me, with great effort, in order that the glory of this saṃkhya may last five thousand (years) undisturbed, in order that in future also the priesthood, without levity, established in the duty of knowledge of the (sacred) scriptures, endowed with the qualities of alepa and cajata, may prosper, having given advice and instruction Religion shall be protected—being endowed with proper and patent virtues, having heard the request of it, having stated that by the theras derived from the great Thera Mahākācyapa, those who live carelessly shall not be tolerated,

having made a sanda of the Vinaya of the law and with the intention that the chief theras should give among the faithful of the disciples who are with each of them the katikāwa which the aedulol made without expanding them, being fit for, not allowing those who dwell to become careless, but uniting them to the burden of study, not allowing them to despise in the lower assembly the Vinaya, the Khuddasikkhā, the Pāṭimokkha, the suttas, the Dasadhamma sutta, and the three Anumāna suttas, together with the Vinaya books, putting far away the conversation with the multitude, he ordered that those who were engaged in study should be continually kept in seclusion. Having purified himself three times having set himself assiduously to and other work, having taken two or three and having interrupted the seclusion not even for a single day, he ordered that each man should direct himself first to what is proper. And having applied himself to these above-mentioned virtues, accomplishing his own and other people's work (?), having organised the burden of study in the above-mentioned way having made the pupils and fellow-priests learn the Mūla sikkhā, the Sekhiya and the Vinaya book, having heard the Sikkha walanda winisa (comp. Zoysa's Report on the Temple libraries, p. 6), having made an abridgement he disposed of the ascetics. Having observed the fasting, having reflected on the Dasadhammasutta, having observed the above-mentioned seclusion, having shown his ability, having learned, in a limited time, the duties of performance, having applied himself to the burden of spiritual insight (Dhamm., p. 80), having spent his days according to the prescript of the four sampajañña's (Dhamm., p. 389), he said: It is right to teach the novices the Herapasikkhā, the Sekhiya, the Dasadhammasutta, the Vinayabook and the play (?), to exercise the parihaarana without despising it, and to observe the seclusion mother and father, two persons, and those which are from the same womb (brothers and sisters), widows and virgins and fellow students (shall take) their food and go begging in the manner indicated above. Medicines for the sick and for the fellow students, and the five ways of collecting alms in forbidden places, except going to the pirit, must be avoided. At a wrong time leave to go to the village must not be given. If leave is given to those who go in order to visit sick people, it is a dukkaṭa āpatti for the teachers to give leave to the avyaktas; if the avyaktas have got no leave to go to the uposatha pawāranam (Khuddasikkhā, vs. 8), knowing the degree of āpatti and anāpatti (guilt and innocence) and making any one of the vyakta sangha responsible (?), leave should be given to them if any one of the priesthood lives in the neighbourhood except having seen it is not allowed to make him dwell (there) for the priesthood in the middle of the night sitting down cross-legged,

it is fit to enjoy sleep, and to recreate their bodies ; in the early morning, having risen, and having set themselves to work with to spend their days sitting, standing, and walking about, to learn pulumu (?), to put on clothes, to clean their teeth, the dāgoba, the botree and the templeground ; the teachers and the theras and the sick should receive their couches and their food and other requisites ; afterwards the priests should descend into the dining-hall and, having taken their gruel and done the duties of the dining-hall, they should inspect the account books the dining, etc., should be done quickly. Having taken the gruel, they should set themselves to work with and pass their days ; having applied themselves to the burden of study with the nyāya (?), the householders and the ascetics should without becoming saṃsaṭṭha (?) up to a certain time spend their days not wealthy except by compassion (alms) having received and being pleased ; when you come together, o bhikkhus, you should do two things—religious conversation or noble silence. Besides these two things, religious conversation and silent attention, (there is) the unprofitable talk (Brahmajāla sutta, p. 10) and love thoughts and evil thoughts (which) they should avoid, in the beginning of the night they should not (?) preach baṇa listening to the religious conversation, etc., not in the succession of the disciples, spending (their time) in the acquisition of spiritual insight ; at midnight, at a lucky moment, sitting cross-legged, it is fit to enjoy sleep, afterwards to pilgrims and ascetics shall rest at the watchhuts, the, the image house, or at some other place ; at all occasions, either in earnest or in joke, unbecoming talk shall not be used by anyone ; towards virgins and little children no harsh or laughing words shall be used, the overseers shall not be angry with the working people who do not know their work, those who only know their own yakaduru and no others shall not give them to others, tom-tom beating by the elders of the priesthood and other utensils except what is at hand for obtaining rain at a place which is not irrigated is good to apply ; such utensils “ the laughter alone increases ” (?), thus having spoken on account of the laughter, it is fit not to expand the sorrow, but to show it alone by word of mouth, those that have their own temples destroyed shall not subdue others, and those that have destroyed other temples shall not stay in their own ; “ by a bhikkhu who does not know writing, and is careful through temptation eagerness,” thus having spoken, it is not right to show eagerness on any occasion ; saluting the dāgoba and the botree, etc., worshipping, etc., using the tooth cleaner it is not allowed to talk loud ; the householders in the villages shall not use patibaddha kathā or visabhāga

kathā : Here is a bhikkhu who either alone or in the middle of the priesthood by inconsiderate talk stands vexing the theras and sits down annoying them and preaches and strokes the head of a young man thus having spoken, appearing in the middle of the priesthood, you should not touch the body with the robe ; and the elders of the priesthood with compassion up to this moment shall preach ; in no place whatever young men touching (?) with their bodies shall ; those that live away from their houses shall not cause perplexion ; after having purified [them] from sin, you should ordain [them] ; after having purified (them) you should admit them to the order ; after having purified them you should give them the nissaya ; one son of a noble family having received the ordination and the admission to the priesthood establishes the order ; (the same in Sinhalese) after having purified (them) you should ordain them, after having purified them you should admit them to the order, after having purified them you should give them the nissaya In this above-mentioned way you should not object to anybody's wishes ; anything that has been ordered in this katikāwa shall not be disobeyed ; if anybody commits a mistake a fine is assessed up to the third time, but if he commits the mistake again without paying the fine up to a month's time he shall be made a prisoner according to the rule in the Vinaya (?) The elders of the gaṇas and the thera shall apply themselves to the burden (of study) and shall not be careless and shall not let the priesthood transgress these rules ; it is right that by the great theras a fine shall be established. Hail !

(140.) Padiwil : Parākramabāhu, the cakrawartti sovereign of happy Laṃkā, descending from ancient princes, has finished (the repairs) of the tanks and ponds for the use of the fields which he made in every part, finding many streams and ponds useless and broken, in the hope of increasing the happiness in this and the next world.

(143.) Dambulla : The sovereign lord of Laṃkā Parākramabāhu, cakrawartti of the dynasty of Kālinga, (surnamed) the heroic and invincible royal warrior, gloriously endued with might, majesty, and wisdom, and, like the placid moon, radiant with cheering and benignant qualities ; the liege lord of Lakdiwa by right of birth, deriving descent from the race of King Wijaya, who extirpated the demons and peopled Ceylon, and was an object of veneration to the other royal dynasties of Dambadiwa, whose renown extended over the whole world ; having dispersed his enemies as the brilliant orb of the sun over the summit of the mountain of the morn dispelleth darkness ; and having extended the canopy of his dominion over the whole island ; enriched the inhabitants who had become impoverished by inordinate taxes, and made them opulent by gifts of lands, cattle, and slaves, by relinquishing the revenues for five years, and